

“THE INFLUENCE OF E-LEARNING AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON PSYCHOLOGICAL INTENTIONS:”

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Abstract

As a preventative step against the spread of the COVID-19 epidemic, educational institutions throughout the world have been shut down. Both local and international students have been severely affected by the closures. For many students, the sudden transition from conventional classroom to online learning has been a source of anxiety and worry. Emotion regulation theory will be utilised to study how e-learning and EI impact Pakistani students' levels of stress, burnout, and academic performance in this environment. The context of the storey. In this research, only 387 students from Ten Indian Colleges and universities were included as subjects. Stress, burnout, and academic performance have all improved significantly as a result of pupils using e-learning and emotional intelligence (EI). These data show that students' stress, exhaustion, and performance may be influenced by online education and EI. Research shows that EI has a substantial influence on a student's mental stress.

Keywords: e-learning, emotional intelligence, study stress, burnout, performance

Introduction

There is no greater obstacle to academic achievement than the psychological toll it takes on students. Students' inspiration, attentiveness, alertness, and social relationships may all be negatively impacted by psychological stress (Unger, 1998). COVID-19 has brought into emphasis the psychological stress of those afflicted by the epidemic. Due to coronavirus, students' mental health and well-being are predicted to be affected by severe measures and delays in commencing colleges and universities throughout the globe. (Cao et al., 2020; UNESCO Education, 2020). Students' ability to manage their emotions is often regarded as a vital aspect of their overall mental well-being. Assignments, tests, quizzes, finals, and other

due dates tie students' emotional well-being to their academic performance in a complex web (Tyng et al., 2017). Students are encouraged to demonstrate patience and a good attitude toward the course of study. Emotional well-being has led to higher results for pupils in the classroom (Corradino and Fogarty, 2016). People in general, health care workers, patients, children, and adults have all been affected emotionally by the COVID-19 outbreak, according to certain research (Chen et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2020). Since the COVID-19 crisis began, no thorough research of Pakistani students' psychological well-being has been carried out. Since students are under a lot of stress, it is important to find ways to alleviate it. Emotional intelligence (EI) and e-learning (online classes) have been studied extensively in the education sector for long-term sustainability. It is rare to find research comparing e-learning (online courses) and emotional intelligence (EI) to student stress, burnout and academic achievement. EI and e-learning have been shown to reduce student anxiety, fatigue, and poor performance in previous studies. This study adds to that work.

Students' sentiments and emotions are intimately tied to their academic and job success, yet career success requires a certain level of excellence. Scholars realised that students' motivations direct their behaviour toward academic achievement and success. Stress and other psychosomatic disorders, such as anxiety, fear, and stress, may lead to a wide range of negative results. The outbreak of COVID-19 has had a significant impact on student educational activities, including online classrooms, the delay of physical events, and the migration of students. "As a result of this, students are experiencing psychological pressure that can lead to anxiety and depression. (Curran and Standage, 2017) As a result of this, Foreign student enrollment is expected to decline in the United States, according to the Institute of International Education's 2020 forecast; the British Council found that 39 percent of Chinese scholars are undecided about withdrawing from their studies in the UK (Martel) (Durnin, 2020). 59.95 percent of all overseas students in China are from Asia, with over 28,023 of them from from our neighbour to the west." Thus, students' stress levels, exhaustion, and overall performance have all been shown to be adversely affected by this kind of negative psychological pressure (Wang et al., 2020). In Pakistan, there has been no study of this kind. An important goal of this research is, thus, a new perspective on Pakistani students studying abroad by examining the impact of online courses and EI on the mental health of Pakistani students studying abroad who find themselves unable to return home.

Work-related stress, burnout, and performance may all be mitigated by emotional intelligence (EI), albeit little has been discovered about the interplay between EI and these other factors so far. Students were asked to participate in an experiment to see whether e-learning (online courses) had an impact on their stress levels at work, as well as their burnout and performance. Emotion regulation theory (Gross, 1998), on which this study is based, states that people evaluate the knowledge, valence, and value significance to manage their feelings and emotions depending on the current circumstances. The ability to perform well under pressure is enhanced in those with strong emotional intelligence (Kirk et al., 2008). EI is a great tool for dealing with the unpleasant consequences of negative feelings. Socially aware people are better at avoiding the repercussions of negative emotions, and their total performance improves as a result, according to Goleman (2001). Research by Garg and colleagues (2016) indicated that

emotional intelligence (EI) has a direct impact on a person's ability to adapt and perform at their best in each given scenario.

The EI assists people in determining their expectations and the best course of action during times of uncertainty. Students are often confronted with such unplanned circumstances throughout their academic careers. Academically, they must meet the requirements of their curriculum by displaying good emotions like patience and concentration, as well as a sense of optimism and pride. An increase in psychological stress might have a negative impact on productivity and the risk of burnout, among other things. When it comes to students' work performance, EI may assist to alleviate the effects of burnout as well as study stress.

“CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Emotional Intelligence”

Salovey and Mayer classified the idea of emotional intelligence (EI) after it was first proposed in the 1920s (1990). Observational self-awareness is defined as "the capacity to discriminate between one's own and other people's mental states and emotions, as well as practise using this knowledge to direct one's own thoughts and behaviours" EI aims for psychological well-being and achievement in life, such as academic success job performance and work-related stress. According to Stevens et al. (2019), a study on the relationship between EI and psychological stress indicated that emotionally intelligent persons are more confident; they are also happier; and they are more social.

Erözkan (2013) discovered that pupils with high levels of EI were better able to deal with psychological stress than those with lower levels of EI. EI and stress coping strategies have been linked in this research by Fteiha and Awwad (2020) as well. Those with a greater degree of emotional intelligence (EI) are better equipped to cope with stressful situations, according to their research. Despite several research, the impact of emotional intelligence (EI) on academic achievement, burnout, and study stress has gotten only intermittent attention in Pakistan.

“Emotional Intelligence, Work Stress, Burnout, and Performance”

It is a person's capacity to recognise and regulate their own self-sensitive behaviours and emotions that is referred to as "emotional intelligence." As a collection of non-cognitive abilities and skills, EI helps people cope with the demands and stressors of their environment. Those with high emotional intelligence (EI) are better equipped to cope with stressful situations, according to researchers.

In light of the academic demands, it is reasonable to argue that EI help students cope with their stress and improve their academic performance. In addition to managing their physical and emotional well-being, students must also deal with the pressures of schoolwork, including tests, projects, presentations, and other forms of written and spoken communication. According to Enns et al. (2018), good pressure management is linked to a high EI. It is his belief that kids who have developed emotional intelligence are better able to handle difficult situations in the classroom. Academic success is more likely to be achieved by students with high emotional

intelligence (EI). A student's well-being and academic achievement are said to be influenced by their emotional intelligence (EI).

In the academic career of a student, occupational stress and burnout are commonplace. In a growing country's lack of resources, bad working conditions, energy shortages, and inadequate management exacerbate students' already high levels of stress and burnout (Ali, 2012). Due to their mental and physical health, students' ability to study and succeed in school is significantly affected. Friedman (2014) stated that a student's physical and mental health might be adversely affected by severe psychological stress. "According to Karimi et al. (2014), our total reaction to stress and burnout is heavily dependent on feelings and feelings. High levels of emotional intelligence (EI)" have been shown to reduce burnout and stress in the workplace, as well as promote satisfaction and professional growth (Na stasa, 2010). Students' ability to cope with stress, stay healthy, and do well academically is negatively impacted by EI (MacCann et al., 2020).

As a result of being trapped in their home countries, students' physical absenteeism rose by more than 15% over the last 15 months, which generated psychological strain, worse academic accomplishment and large gaps between practical skills and development (Coe et al., 2020). As a consequence, Bonal and González (2020) discovered that students from low-income nations, in particular, lose out on educational opportunities when they do not attend university. During a crisis, EI has been shown to have a substantial influence on the prevention of crises spiralling out of control. A study by suggests that EI helps students avoid stress and burnout, which in turn improves their academic results. Observed that those with greater intellectual abilities are better able to handle stressful conditions. It was shown that a high degree of emotional intelligence (EI) has a direct influence on students' levels of burnout in stressful situations, which in turn led to better student performance (Yusoff et al., 2021). "Many research have examined the link between emotional intelligence (EI) and nurses' job productivity. But this research examines the impact of emotional intelligence (EI) on the performance of students trapped in Pakistan owing to the COVID-19 crisis." The following is an educated guess by the authors:

H1: A high association exists between students' emotional intelligence and their capacity to succeed in the job.

H2: Students' levels of emotional intelligence and anxiety over their studies are strongly correlated.

H3: When it comes to students, emotional intelligence and exhaustion have a strong negative connotation.

“Online Classes, Study Stress, Burnout, and Performance”

During this year's COVID-19, there was a lot of interest in the educational institution's facilities (Chatterjee and Chakraborty, 2021). There are a plethora of options for taking courses online these days (Nash, 2020). An educational institution's online curriculum proved difficult to establish. According to Mishra et al. (2020), advanced nations had online courses before the

epidemic. However, no school was prepared for a total shift to online courses. Pakistani students' responses to online courses vary from those of students in the United States, according to empirical study (Bojovic' et al., 2020), although the results are similar. Inadequate online learning systems are cited by Williams et al. (2011) as one of the reasons. For students in places where there are few or no Internet connections, a regular classroom setting is not an option because of the lack of network flexibility (Williams et al., 2011). According to Adnan and Anwar (2020), who conducted research at COVID-19 on Pakistani students' feelings of anxiety and depression in the face of online learning, it has been shown that online education might have a negative impact on pupils in developing countries. Stressed students are more likely to have problems with the Internet, technology, "finances, and other educational resources, such as experimentation labs (Adnan and Anwar, 2020)."

Pupils' psychological stress has been exacerbated by the coronavirus pandemic, which has resulted in kids being quarantined at home. Both professors and students have seen a decline in traditional classroom activities including group projects, lab work, and experimentation as a consequence of the rise of online schools. As a result, both pupils and instructors are suffering from stress and exhaustion as a result of all of this. Students who spend most of their time at home and are less physically active have a detrimental influence on their academic achievement (Chandra, 2020). Studies conducted by Rohman et al. (2020) found that students' mental and physical health suffered as a direct result of the increased academic pressure they experienced as a result of taking courses online. The COVID-19 pandemics, according to Sahu (2020), have caused numerous psychological shocks and a severe impact on students' mental well-being, leading directly to acute job stress and anxiety. During the coronavirus epidemic in China, Cao et al. (2020) studied the psychological impact on university students. As a result of their research, they discovered that pupils' performance suffered and that they were under a great deal of psychological stress. Uncertainty has been shown to have a detrimental effect on pupils' academic progress and on their psychological stress levels

In contrast to improved family amenities, Jger and Blaabk (2020) said that online courses inhibited students from developing their learning abilities. For kids from low-income households and rural places, the question arises "how this method serves pupils?" (Yen, 2020) A significant number of pupils come from low-income households, hence (Fry and Cilluffo, 2019). Rural and low-income students have fewer or no options for online education owing to a dearth of resources and the need for extensive experimental testing in the labs. In the same way, the expense of taking online programmes is another barrier (Adam et al., 2020). Online courses were shown to be a substantial cause to stress and burnout in research by Sundarasan and colleagues (2020). Student psychological intents were adversely influenced by the financial restrictions, online class hurdles and academic performance that were recorded by the researchers. Many children are concerned about dropping out of school as a result of the ineffective teaching methods, according to Choi (2020). Because of this, online courses have a significant influence on the student's mental strain and academic achievement (Jiang et al., 2021). Thus, we came up with the following theory:

H4: Taking online education has a detrimental impact on a student's productivity at work.

H5: Online classrooms have a good impact on student stress.

H6: Students who take their lessons online report higher rates of mental and physical exhaustion.

Theoretical Framework

For educational, psychological and managerial research, emotional intelligence is a key component. One of its main goals is to help people better understand their emotional responses, as well as identify their experiences with a wide variety of emotions (Bliss, 2006). It also has to do with how to cope with disappointments in one's emotions, how to change one's behaviours, and how to avoid emotional exhaustion and stress. Researchers Richards and Pryce (2006) contend that having a high degree of emotional intelligence (EI) makes people more adept at handling stress and burnout while also enhancing their overall productivity and quality of life. Higher levels of emotional intelligence (EI) are better able to deal with the causes of stress and burnout, resulting in better job performance (Alonazi, 2020). Stress and exhaustion caused by the pandemic may be lessened by those who have a high degree of emotional intelligence (EI), say researchers Sadovyy et al. (2021). To put it another way, during the present epidemic, emotionally intelligent people outperform those with a low degree of EI in terms of their productivity. As a result, educational activities have been shifted to the new setting in order to preserve the growth of kids. Students' academic performance may be boosted by emotional intelligence (EI), which has been recognised as a critical component of the learning process in the previous decade (Cleveland-Innes and Campbell, 2012). Online learning has been linked to a student's ability to manage their emotions. Teachers anticipate pupils who have strong emotional intelligence (EI) abilities to respond more effectively than those who lack this ability. As a result of the emotional competences, kids' performance in the classroom may be enhanced (McKnight, 2013). "An increased EI has been shown to be associated with improved stress management, according to Enns et al. (2018)."' As stated by Enns and co-authors (2018), an emotionally intelligent person is better able to deal with stressful events and educational hurdles.

Emotional intelligence (EI) has been shown to be closely linked to psychological management in a variety of professions, including education and academic success (Williford, 2010). EI talents help students adjust to an unknown circumstance appropriately and encourage them to come up with creative solutions, "which may affect their intellectual skills and lead to a standard academic achievement. Studies have shown that students" ability to succeed in online and remote learning courses is greatly influenced by their emotional intelligence (EI). According to Grandey (2000), those with high levels of emotional intelligence (EI) decreased stress, burnout, and increased productivity. Emotional intelligence (EI) has been shown to minimise workplace stress and conflict (interpersonal and environmental), as well as improve job results, by Wu et al. (2007) study.

As EI rises, so does the level of stress. Furthermore, Márquez and colleagues (2006) discovered that kids with greater EI were more likely to succeed in school. People with high emotional intelligence (EI) tend to be more successful than those who lack it, according to psychologists. Few research have examined EI as a predictor of success in online courses, despite the fact that EI has been shown to have a positive impact on other aspects of life. As a result of COVID-19, online education will continue for the foreseeable future. A greater level of emotional intelligence is linked to a higher level of psychological functioning. As a result, the authors look at the potential moderating effects of EI on online courses, study stress, burnout, and performance.

Research Methods

Data Collection Process

In order to gather data from students in COVID-19, the research has adopted a quantitative technique.

Because it is difficult to collect a full sample frame, the convenience sampling strategy was used. The results may be theoretically generalised because of the sample design. "Research assistants who had been professionally trained in utilising Google surveys and social media platforms like as Facebook, WeChat, and WhatsApp were used by the authors to assure the correctness of their results." Participants were required to express written agreement to participate in this research before completing the questionnaire. There were a total of 429 completed questionnaires, of which 387 were found to be suitable for this study by the authors themselves.

Measurements

Emotional Intelligence

"Scale designed by UCLA academics and published in Schutte et al was used to measure Emotional Intelligence (EI) (2001). (1998). Self-reporting questions are included in this exam's total of 32. Students were asked to rate their level of agreement with each of the 32 statements on a Likert scale of 1 to 5, where 1 meant strongly disagree, and 5 meant strongly agree." "When I am in a good mood, I am more motivated, and I am able to solve difficulties more easily." The EI scale's Cronbach's alpha was 0.88.

Stress

Students' stress levels during the coronavirus epidemic were specifically targeted while developing the items for the psychological stress test. From "Not at all stressful" to "Extremely stressful," there are seven things included on a 5-point Likert scale of stress. The instrument's design was influenced by theories about how stress affects the mind and body (Lazarus and Folkman, 1984). The COVID-19 pandemic included a wide range of stressors, and each question was tailored to address those in the most detail. An example item reads, "I am frustrated by the amount of work and lack of resources that I am facing." In terms of reliability, this scale has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.83.

Burnout

“Weakness (five items), depersonalization (four items), and personal success (two items) were all shown to be significant indicators of burnout in a study of 15 people (Schaufeli et al., 2002).” (Six items). Items like "Do you feel emotionally fatigued because of your online studies" and "how frequently do you feel emotionally drained throughout the classes" are good examples. The burnout scale's total Cronbach's alpha was 0.87.

Performance

According to Cooper and Petrides, 12-item measures for assessing a student's emotional well-being, emotional regulation, and social skills were used to evaluate academic success (2010). The questions were developed based on the relationships between academic performance and emotional intelligence (EI). The Likert scale has a range of "high-performance score" (0) to "poor performance" (100). (4). this scale has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.89.

E-Learning

An 11-item measure designed by e-learning professionals was used to evaluate students' academic progress, stress, and burnout (Chakraborty et al., 2020). For example, a physical classroom is superior to an online programme in terms of education. We also inquired about the frequency with which students were happy or unsatisfied with their education experience in general. In terms of a Likert scale, "often pleased" (0) to "often dissatisfied" (4) was specified (4). A Cronbach's alpha of 0.86 was found throughout the whole dataset.

Results

There are several ways to test discriminant validity, but one of the most common is to look at the correlations between the measures of interest and the measurements of other constructs. “It is shown in Table 1 how well these variables correlate, as well as their averages and standard deviations Academic achievement and study stress have a statistically “significant link with emotional intelligence (EI), according to the findings of this research. There is a strong link between exhaustion and emotional intelligence” ($p = 0.01$).” When e-learning is correlated with academic achievement, stress, or burnout (p value of 0.01), the correlations are all negative. This is true for all three variables.

Structural Model

We utilised the structural model measurement to look at the relationship between our two main variables. For the usual regression analysis of parameter paths, see Table 2. “Research indicated that EI has a positive influence on academic achievement ($p = 0.001$). According to Hypothesis 1, 2, 3, and 4, the EI had a negative and significant impact on study stress and burnout ($p = 0.001$). Hypothesis 4 is supported by the positive influence of e-learning on academic success ($p = 0.21$)” whereas Hypothesis 5 and 6 are supported by the negative impact on study stress and burnout.

Moderation Analysis

EI and e-learning may have an interaction (moderating) effect on academic achievement, burnout, and study stress, according to the findings of this research. EI with e-learning has a substantial influence on academic achievement as indicated in Table 2. Hypothesis 7 is thus supported.

According to our findings, Table 2 shows that EI may moderate the effects of e-learning in terms of stress and burnout, which supports Hypotheses 8 and 9 in this regard. Study stress and burnout may be reduced by using EI in combination with online learning, which is a promising finding.

“E-learning and EI products were used to create an average-centered interaction term that was used to map interactions. When two standard variables are analysed simultaneously, the interaction between them is a significant predictor, as shown in Table 2. It was shown that the interaction term predicted academic performance, study stress and burnout with thorough support for the proposed model. Students with higher levels of emotional intelligence (EI) showed less of a negative correlation between e-learning and test scores, which in turn reduced the negative impact of e-learning on test scores.” “There was a greater negative link between e-learning and academic success for those who had low emotional intelligence (EI).

Students with poor emotional intelligence (EI) exhibited a strong correlation between online learning and stress, whereas students with high EI had a weak link. Students with low levels of emotional intelligence (EI) are more likely to experience burnout as a result of online learning than students with greater levels of EI.”

“TABLE 1 | Correlations analysis.

Variables	Mean	(SD)	α	1	2	3	4	5
1. Academic performance	3.87	0.21	0.86	1				
2. Study stress	2.84	0.45	0.82	-0.15	1			
3. Burnout	3.01	0.44	0.86	-0.21*	0.26*	1		
4. EI	4.22	0.76	0.87	0.46**	-0.37*	-0.34**	1	
5. E-Learning	3.97	0.48	0.86	-0.36**	0.43**	0.41***	-0.23**	1

Table 2:

Parameter tested correlation	Mean values	P value	Hypothesis relation
EI→ Academic performance	0.36	0.00	Accepted
EI→ Study stress	-0.13	0.00	Accepted
EI→ Burnout	-0.22	0.00	Accepted
E-Learning→ Academic performance	-0.20	0.01	Accepted
E-Learning→ Study stress	0.39	0.01	Accepted
E-Learning→ Burnout	0.32	0.01	Accepted
E-Learning EI→ Academic performance	0.19	0.00	Accepted
E-Learning EI→ Study stress	-0.15	0.00	Accepted
E-Learning EI→ Burnout	-0.17	0.01	Accepted”

Discussion

Currently, pupils are reporting that the COVID-19 epidemic is interfering with their studies. Numerous students have been compelled to abandon their studies because of this. “There is a direct correlation between students’ academic performance and psychological objectives and the absence of their college campuses, their friends and professors, going to the library, doing experiments in laboratories, participating in group discussions, and other activities.”

According to our findings, Pakistani students are particularly sensitive to the demands of online education. High levels of stress and exhaustion, as well as a poor level of academic achievement, plague them. Study stress and burnout were lower among kids with high EI, who also performed well in school. Electronic learning has been shown to impact academic achievement, stress in the learning process and burnout when combined with Emotional Intelligence (EI). A high degree of emotional intelligence (EI) was shown to be an important factor in student achievement. The findings of this investigation, then, confirmed all of our predictions.

In addition, the study found that Pakistani students' psychological intents during the COVID-19 epidemic were influenced by two crucial factors: “In this study, the results indicate that e-learning and emotional intelligence (EI) are vital to a student's success in the classroom. There is a strong correlation between a student's mental strain and their likelihood of quitting online courses and engaging in bad behaviour towards their education.” EI may be able to manage e-learning, leading in decreased levels of stress and burnout in students and an improvement in academic achievement, according to this study. (c) Emotional intelligence (EI) is a talent that can be learnt and honed through practise and repetition. According to Yilmaz (2009), he did a research project. Students' emotional intelligence (EI) may be improved by providing them with EI training programmes, according to this author.

There is evidence to suggest that students who are better able to cope with and control their emotions in the face of psychological stress and burnout have higher levels of well-being than

those who are not as adept at managing both positive and negative emotions. An educational institution or online course offering emotional training may improve the learning experience, as shown by the findings of this study. Learning emotional intelligence (EI) may help students better handle and excel in a wide range of demanding and unexpected situations (Herrera et al., 2020). It is similar to the Lam and Kirby (2002) research, which found that EI might help students deal more successfully with both their academic and personal challenges and their psychological stress. There has been a decrease in the number of EI students who report feeling a lot of pressure throughout the course of their studies (Adeyemo and Ogunyemi, 2005).

One of the most important characteristics of students, according to Cazan and Nastasa (2015), is their ability to demonstrate interest in and commitment to their academic studies. Successful academic progress necessitates that students demonstrate the ability to deal with pressure, have a positive outlook on their work, and engage with their lecturers. Physical and emotional challenges are especially important because they help build interpersonal skills, “but they also need excellent relationships with friends and family, teachers, and other professionals in very challenging and unexpected situations.” They examined the link between emotional issues and student viewpoints, and discovered that the stress and burnout of students became increasingly apparent. It follows that emotional control and management are essential for a good academic performance.

“Conclusion and Limitations of the Study”

To sum up, this research investigates the links between e-learning, emotional intelligence (EI), academic stress and burnout, as well as student academic performance throughout the worldwide pandemic. Our results provide strong evidence that EI is capable of dealing with the stress and adverse effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, as has been suggested in prior research (Chandra, 2020). Similarly, Estrada et al. (2021) According to our own research, pupils' academic performance increased and their stress levels decreased as a result of exposure to emotional intelligence (EI). According to the conclusions of this research, students in online courses endure significant levels of psychological strain, and EI development and training programmes should be part of their academic curriculum. Students who participate in EI training and development programmes have an easier time managing and coping with stressful circumstances (Drigas and Papoutsi, 2020), as well as better social and academic outcomes (Wang, 2019). Thus, pupils' capacity to deal with and handle uncertain circumstances may be improved, which might lead to improved academic achievement.

There were several drawbacks to this research. First, the use of self-report evaluation in this study might raise issues about response biases. A future research might replicate this model on other professions, such as university professors, organisation executives, and workers of multinational corporations, in order to improve the generalizability of the findings. For this study, researchers looked at the relationship between e-learning and abroad students' psychological intents. As a result, examining the effect of other factors would be intriguing (e.g., IQ and cultural intelligence). One of the study's main limitations is the minimal number of participants. Fewer than 400 people were included in the study, with just 10 Chinese

University students stuck in Pakistan being examined. A larger sample of data, drawn from a variety of nations, might be used in future research.

References

- Adam, T., Kaye, T., and Haßler, B. (2020). The Maldives and Sri Lanka: Question and Answer Session (EdTech Hub Helpdesk Response No. 18). EdTech Hub. Adeyemo, D. A., and Ogunyemi, B. (2005). Emotional intelligence and self-
- Efficacy as predictors of occupational stress among academic staff in a Nigerian University. *J. Organiz. Learn. Leadersh.* 7, 1–14.
- Adnan, M., and Anwar, K. (2020). Online learning amid the COVID-19 pandemic: students' perspectives. *Online Sub.* 2, 45–51. doi: 10.33902/JPSP.2020261309
- Aktekin, M., Karaman, T., Senol, Y. Y., Erdem, S., Erengin, H., and Akaydin, M. (2001). Anxiety, depression and stressful life events among medical students: a prospective study in Antalya, Turkey. *Med. Educ.* 35, 12–17. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2923.2001.00726.x
- Ali, T. (2012). A case study of the common difficulties experienced by high school students in chemistry classroom in Gilgit-Baltistan (Pakistan). *SAGE Open* 2, 1–13. doi: 10.1177/2158244012447299
- Alonazi, W. B. (2020). The impact of emotional intelligence on job performance during COVID-19 crisis: a cross-sectional analysis. *Psychol. Res. Behav. Manag.* 13, 749–757. doi: 10.2147/PRBM.S263656
- Altbach, P. G., and de Wit, H. (2020). Pos pandemic outlook for HE is bleakest for the poorest. *University World News*. Available online at: [fromhttps://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20200402152914362](https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20200402152914362) (accessed April 4, 2020).
- Austin, E. J., Evans, P., Goldwater, R., and Potter, V. (2005). A preliminary study of emotional intelligence, empathy and exam performance in first year medical students. *Pers. Individ. Dif.* 39, 1395–1405. doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2005.04.014
- Bar-On, R., Handley, R., and Fund, S. (2006). "The impact of emotional intelligence on performance," in *Linking Emotional Intelligence and Performance at Work: Current Research Evidence with Individuals and Group*, eds V. U. Druskat, F. Sala, G. Mount (Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum), 3–19.
- Bayram, N., and Bilgel, N. (2008). The prevalence and socio-demographic correlations of depression, anxiety and stress among a group of University students. *Soc. Psychiatry Psychiatr. Epidemiol.* 43, 667–672. doi: 10.1007/s00127-008-0345-x
- Bentler, P. M. (1990). Comparative fit indexes in structural models. *Psychol. Bull.* 107:238. doi: 10.1037/0033-2909.107.2.238
- Berenson, R., Boyles, G., and Weaver, A. (2008). Emotional intelligence as a predictor of success in online learning. *Int. Rev. Res. Open Distribut. Learn.* 9, 1–16. doi: 10.19173/irrodl.v9i2.385
- Bliss, S. E. (2006). The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on a Modern Organizational Leader's Ability to Make Effective Decisions. Available online at: <http://eqi.org/mgtpaper/~htm> (accessed March 03, 2021).
- Bojovic', Ž., Bojovic', P. D., Vujošević, D., and Šuh, J. (2020). Education in times of crisis: rapid transition to distance learning. *Comput. Appl. Eng. Educ.* 28, 1467–1489. doi: 10.1002/cae.22318
- Bonal, X., and González, S. (2020). The impact of lockdown on the learning gap: family and school divisions in times of crisis. *Int. Rev. Educ.* 66, 635–655. doi: 10.1007/s11159-020-09860-z
- Byrne, B. M. (1994). *Structural Equation Modeling with EQS and EQS/Windows: Basic concepts, Applications, and Programming*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

- Cao, W., Fang, Z., Hou, G., Han, M., Xu, X., Dong, J., et al. (2020). The psychological impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on college students in China. *Psychiatry Res.* 287, 1–5. doi: 10.1016/j.psychres.2020.112934
- Carmeli, A., Yitzhak-Halevy, M., and Weisberg, J. (2009). The relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological wellbeing. *J. Manag. Psychol.* 24, 66–78. doi: 10.1108/02683940910922546
- Cazan, A. M., and Nařstasã, L. E. (2015). Emotional intelligence, satisfaction with life and burnout among University students. *Procedia* 180, 1574–1578. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.02.309
- Chakraborty, P., Mittal, P., Gupta, M. S., Yadav, S., and Arora, A. (2020). Opinion of students on online education during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Hum. Behav. Emerg. Technol.* 3, 357–365. doi: 10.1002/hbe2.240
- Chandra, Y. (2020). Online education during COVID-19: perception of academic stress and emotional intelligence coping strategies among college students. *Asian Educ. Dev. Stud.* 10, 229–238. doi: 10.1108/AEDS-05-2020-0097
- Chandra, Y., and Mathur, K. (2016). Perception of entrepreneurial orientation, aspiration and its impact on emotional wellbeing: challenges for the future entrepreneurs. *Research Trends in Economics, Finance and Human Resource Management*, Nirma University, 227–237.
- Chatterjee, I., and Chakraborty, P. (2021). Use of information communication technology by medical educators amid covid-19 pandemic and beyond. *J. Educ. Technol. Syst.* 49, 310–324. doi: 10.1177/0047239520966996
- Chen, Q., Liang, M., Li, Y., Guo, J., Fei, D., Wang, L., et al. (2020). Mental health care for medical staff in China during the COVID-19 outbreak. *Lancet Psychiatry* 7, 15–16. doi: 10.1016/S2215-0366(20)30078-X
- Choi, B. (2020). I’m Afraid of not succeeding in learning: Introducing an instrument to measure higher education students’ fear of failure in learning. *Stud. High. Educ.* doi: 10.1080/03075079.2020.1712691. [Epub ahead of print].
- Cleveland-Innes, M., and Campbell, P. (2012). Emotional presence, learning, and the online learning environment. *Int. Rev. Res. Open Distrib. Learn.* 13, 269–292. doi: 10.19173/irrodl.v13i4.1234
- Coe, R., Weidmann, B., Coleman, R., and Kay, J. (2020). Impact of school closures on the attainment gap: rapid evidence assessment. *Education Endowment Foundation*, London, 1–26. doi: 10.21820/23987073.2020.8.26
- Cooper, A., and Petrides, K. V. (2010). A psychometric analysis of the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire–Short Form (TEIQue–SF) using item response theory. *J. Pers. Assess.* 92, 449–457. doi: 10.1080/00223891.2010.497426
- Corradino, C., and Fogarty, K. (2016). Positive emotions and academic achievement. Available online at: https://wp.nyu.edu/steinhardt-appsych_opus/positive-emotions-and-academic-achievement/ (accessed January 11, 2021).
- Curran, T., and Standage, M. (2017). Psychological needs and the quality of student engagement in physical education: teachers as key facilitators. *J. Teach. Phys. Educ.* 36, 262–276. doi: 10.1123/jtpe.2017-0065
- Drigas, A., and Papoutsis, C. (2020). The need for emotional intelligence training education in critical and stressful situations: the case of Covid-19. *Int. J. Recent Contributions Eng. Sci. IT* 8, 20–36. doi: 10.3991/ijes.v8i3.17235
- Durnin, M. (2020). Covid-19 Update: China Survey Results. London: British Council. Available online at: https://education-services.britishcouncil.org/insights-blog/covid-19-update-chinasurvey-results?_ga=2.183165667.436377671.1596516253~1764238916.1596516253.
- Enns, A., Eldridge, G. D., Montgomery, C., and Gonzalez, V. M. (2018). Perceived stress, coping strategies, and emotional intelligence: A cross-sectional study of university students in helping disciplines. *Nurse Educ. Today.* 68, 226–231. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2018.06.012
- Ergur, D. O. (2009). How can education professionals become emotionally intelligent? *Procedia* 1, 1023–1028. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2009.01.183

- Erözkan, A. (2013). Exploring the relationship between perceived emotional intelligence and coping skills of undergraduate students. *J. Hum. Sci.* 10, 1537–1549.
- Estrada, M., Monferrer, D., Rodríguez, A., and Moliner, M. Á. (2021). Does emotional intelligence influence academic performance? The role of compassion and engagement in education for sustainable development. *Sustainability* 13:1721. doi: 10.3390/su13041721
- Fiorilli, C., Farina, E., Buonomo, I., Costa, S., Romano, L., Larcán, R., et al. (2020). Trait emotional intelligence and school burnout: the mediating role of resilience and academic anxiety in high school. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 17:3058. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17093058
- Friedman, G. (2014). Student stress, burnout and engagement. Dissertation, 1–119.
- Fry, R., and Cilluffo, A. (2019). A rising share of undergraduates are from poor families, especially at less selective colleges. Pew Research Center.
- Fteiha, M., and Awwad, N. (2020). Emotional intelligence and its relationship with stress coping style. *Health Psychol. Open* 7, 1–9. doi: 10.1177/2055102920970416
- Garg, R., Levin, E., and Tremblay, L. (2016). Emotional intelligence: impact on post-secondary academic achievement. *Soc. Psychol. Educ.* 19, 627–642. doi: 10.1007/s11218-016-9338-x
- Goleman, D. (2001). “An EI-based theory of performance,” in *The Emotionally Intelligent Workplace: How to Select for, Measure, and Improve Emotional Intelligence in Individuals, Groups, and Organizations*, eds C. Cherniss and D. Goleman (San Francisco, CA: John Wiley & Sons), 27–44.
- Grandey, A. A. (2000). Emotional regulation in the workplace: a new way to conceptualize emotional labor. *J. Occup. Health Psychol.* 5, 95–110. doi: 10.1037/1076-8998.5.1.95
- Gross, J. J. (1998). The emerging field of emotion regulation: an integrative review. *Rev. Gen. Psychol.* 2, 271–299. doi: 10.1037/1089-2680.2.3.271
- Halimi, F., AlShammari, I., and Navarro, C. (2020). Emotional intelligence and academic achievement in higher education. *J. Appl. Res. High. Educ.* 12, 377–402. doi: 10.1108/JARHE-11-2019-0286
- Han, H., and Johnson, S. D. (2012). Relationship between students’ emotional intelligence, social bond, and interactions in online learning. *J. Educ. Technol. Soc.* 15, 78–89.
- Herrera, L., Al-Lal, M., and Mohamed, L. (2020). Academic achievement, self-concept, personality and emotional intelligence in primary education analysis by gender and cultural group. *Front. Psychol.* 10:3075. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.03075
- Ioannidou, F., and Konstantikaki, V. (2008). Empathy and emotional intelligence: what is it really about? *Int. J. Caring Sci.* 1, 118–123.
- Jæger, M. M., and Blaabæk, E. H. (2020). Inequality in learning opportunities during Covid-19: evidence from library takeout. *Res. Soc. Stratif. Mobil.* 68, 1–13. doi: 10.1016/j.rssm.2020.100524
- Jenaabadi, H., Nastiezaie, N., and Safarzaie, H. (2017). The relationship of academic burnout and academic stress with academic self-efficacy among graduate students. *Educ. Rev.* 49, 65–76. doi: 10.15804/tner.2017.49.3.05
- Jiang, H., Islam, A. A., Gu, X., and Spector, J. M. (2021). Online learning satisfaction in higher education during the COVID-19 pandemic: A regional comparison between Eastern and Western Chinese universities. *Educ. Inf. Technol.* 1–23. doi: 10.1007/s10639-021-10519-x.
- Karimi, L., Leggat, S. G., Donohue, L., Farrell, G., and Couper, G. E. (2014). Emotional rescue: the role of emotional intelligence and emotional labour on well-being and job-stress among community nurses. *J. Adv. Nurs.* 70, 176–186. doi: 10.1111/jan.12185

- Kirk, B. A., Schutte, N. S., and Hine, D. W. (2008). Development and preliminary validation of an emotional self-efficacy scale. *Pers. Individ. Dif.* 45, 432–436. doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2008.06.010
- Koman, E. S., and Wolff, S. B. (2008). Emotional intelligence competencies in the team and team leader: a multi-level examination of the impact of emotional intelligence on team performance. *J. Manage. Dev.* 27, 55–75. doi: 10.1108/02621710810840767
- Krishnan, R., Mahphoth, M. H., Ahmad, N. A. F., and A'yudin, N. A. (2018). The influence of emotional intelligence on employee job performance: a Malaysian case study. *Int. J. Acad. Res. Bus. Soc. Sci.* 8, 234–246. doi: 10.6007/IJARBS/v8-i5/4097
- Lam, L. T., and Kirby, S. L. (2002). Is emotional intelligence an advantage? An exploration of the impact of emotional and general intelligence on individual performance. *J. Soc. Psychol.* 142, 133–143. doi: 10.1080/00224540209603891
- Lazarus, R. S., and Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, Appraisal, and Coping*. New York, NY: Springer publishing company.
- MacCann, C., Jiang, Y., Brown, L. E., Double, K. S., Bucich, M., and Minbashian, A. (2020). Emotional intelligence predicts academic performance: a meta-analysis. *Psychol. Bull.* 146, 150–186. doi: 10.1037/bul0000219
- Márquez, P. G. O., Martín, R. P., and Brackett, M. A. (2006). Relating emotional intelligence to social competence and academic achievement in high school students. *Psicothema.* 18, 118–123.
- Martel, M. (2020). COVID-19 effects on U.S. higher education campuses: From emergency response to future student mobility. Report 2 March, 16.
- McKnight, J. (2013). Using emotional intelligence as a basis for developing an online faculty guide for emotional awareness. *J. Instruct. Res.* 2, 19–29. doi: 10.9743/JIR.2013.2.13
- Mikolajczak, M., Menil, C., and Luminet, O. (2007). Explaining the protective effect of trait emotional intelligence regarding occupational stress: exploration of emotional labour processes. *J. Res. Pers.* 41, 1107–1117. doi: 10.1016/j.jrp.2007.01.003
- Ministry of Education in China (2019). Statistics of studying in China in 2018. Available online at: http://en.moe.gov.cn/documents/reports/202102/t20210209_513095.html (accessed February 24, 2021).
- Mishra, L., Gupta, T., and Shree, A. (2020). Online teaching-learning in higher education during lockdown period of COVID-19 pandemic. *Int. J. Educ. Res. Open* 1:100012. doi: 10.1016/j.ijedro.2020.100012
- Mo, Y., Deng, L., Zhang, L., Lang, Q., Liao, C., Wang, N., et al. (2020). Work stress among Chinese nurses to support Wuhan in fighting against COVID-19 epidemic. *J. Nurs. Manag.* 28, 1002–1009. doi: 10.1111/jonm.13014
- Mohzan, M. A. M., Hassan, N., and AbdHalil, N. (2013). The influence of emotional intelligence on academic achievement. *Procedia* 90, 303–312. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.07.095
- Moreno-Fernandez, J., Ochoa, J., Lopez-Aliaga, I., Alferez, M., Gomez-Guzman, M., LopezOrtega, S., et al. (2020). Lockdown, emotional intelligence, academic engagement and burnout in pharmacy students during the quarantine. *Pharmacy* 8:194. doi: 10.3390/pharmacy8040194
- Mulaik, S. A., James, L. R., Van Alstine, J., Bennett, N., Lind, S., and Stilwell, C.D. (1989). Evaluation of goodness-of-fit indices for structural equation models. *Psychol. Bull.* 105:430. doi: 10.1037/0033-2909.105.3.430
- Naquin, M. R., and Gilbert, G. G. (1996). College students' smoking behavior, perceived stress, and coping styles. *J. Drug Educ.* 26, 367–376. doi: 10.2190/MTG0-DCCE-YR29-JLT3

- Nash, C. (2020). Report on digital literacy in academic meetings during the 2020 COVID-19 lockdown. *Challenges* 11:20. doi: 10.3390/challe11020020
- Naștasa, L. E. (2010). “Developing emotional intelligence of students in psychology through the experiential group,” in *Validation Studies and Applied Research of Psychology and Psychotherapy Unification (in Education, Personal Development and Clinical)*, ed I. Mitrofan (Bucharest: Bucharest University Press), 565–802.
- Palos, R., Costea, I., Munteanu, A., and Drobot, L. (2010). The necessity to adapt instruction to the students’ intellectual development. *Procedia* 5, 323–327. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.07.097
- Pedrosa, A. L., Bitencourt, L., Fróes, A. C. F., Cazumbá, M. L. B., Campos, R. G. B., de Brito, S. B. C. S., et al. (2020). Emotional, behavioral, and psychological Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Front. Psychol.* 11:566212. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.566212
- Petrides, K. V., Frederickson, N., and Furnham, A. (2004). The role of trait emotional intelligence in academic performance and deviant behavior at school. *Pers. Individ. Differ.* 36, 277–293. doi: 10.1016/S0191-8869(03)00084-9
- Por, J., Barriball, L., Fitzpatrick, J., and Roberts, J. (2011). Emotional intelligence: its relationship to stress, coping, well-being and professional performance in nursing students. *Nurse Educ. Today* 31, 855–860. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2010.12.023
- Pugh, E. (2008). Recognising emotional intelligence in professional standards for teaching. *Pract. Res. High. Educ.* 2, 3–12.
- Rezvani, A., Ashkanasy, N., and Khosravi, P. (2020). Key attitudes: unlocking the relationships between emotional intelligence and performance in construction projects. *J. Construct. Eng. Manage.* 146:1803. doi: 10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0001803
- Richards, D., and Pryce, J. (2006). EI, wellbeing and performance. *Comp. Emot. Intell. Q.* 13, 41–46.
- Rohman, M., Marji, D. A. S., Sugandi, R. M., and Nurhadi, D. (2020). Online learning in higher education during covid-19 pandemic: students’ perceptions. *J. Talent Dev. Excell.* 12, 3644–3651.
- Runcan, P. L., and Iovu, M. B. (2013). Emotional intelligence and life satisfaction in Romanian University students: the mediating role of self-esteem and social support. *Rev. Cercetareșinterventiesociala* 40, 137–148.
- Sadovyy, M., Sánchez-Gómez, M., and Bresó, E. (2021). COVID-19: How the stress generated by the pandemic may affect work performance through the moderating role of emotional intelligence. *Pers. Individ. Dif.* 180:110986. doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2021.110986
- Sahu, P. (2020). Closure of universities due to coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID- 19): impact on education and mental health of students and academic staff. *Cureus* 12:7541. doi: 10.7759/cureus.7541
- Salovey, P., and Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional intelligence. *Imagin. Cogn. Pers.* 9, 185–211. doi: 10.2190/DUGG-P24E-52WK-6CDG
- Schaufeli, W. B., Salanova, M., González-Romá, V., and Bakker, A. B. (2002). The measurement of engagement and burnout: a two sample confirmatory factor analytic approach. *J. Happiness Stud.* 3, 71–92. doi: 10.1023/A:1015630930326
- Schutte, N. S., Malouff, J. M., Hall, L. E., Haggerty, D. J., Cooper, J. T., Golden, C. J., et al. (1998). Development and validation of a measure of emotional intelligence. *Pers. Individ. Dif.* 25, 167–177. doi: 10.1016/S0191-8869(98)00001-4
- Shen, L., Wang, M., and Shen, R. (2009). Affective e-learning: Using “emotional” data to improve learning in pervasive learning environment. *J. Educ. Technol. Soc.* 12, 176–189.

- Stevens, C., Schneider, E., Bederman-Miller, P., and Arcangelo, K. (2019). Exploring the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic stress among students at a small, private college. *Contemp. Iss. Educ. Res.* 12, 93–102. doi: 10.19030/cier.v12i4.10322
- Suhaimi, A. W., Marzuki, N. A., and Mustaffa, C. S. (2014). The relationship between emotional intelligence and interpersonal communication skills in disaster management context: a proposed framework. *Procedia* 155, 110–114. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.10.265
- Suleman, Q., Hussain, I., Syed, M. A., Parveen, R., Lodhi, I. S., and Mahmood, Z. (2019). Association between emotional intelligence and academic success among undergraduates: a cross-sectional study in KUST, Pakistan. *PLoS ONE* 14:219648. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0219468
- Sundarasan, S., Chinna, K., Kamaludin, K., Nurunnabi, M., Baloch, G. M., Khoshaim, H. B., et al. (2020). Psychological impact of COVID-19 and lockdown among University students in Malaysia: implications and policy recommendations. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 17:6206. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17176206
- Tesar, M. (2020). Towards a post-Covid-19 ‘new normality?’ physical and social distancing, the move to online and higher education. *Policy Futures Educ.* 18, 556–559. doi: 10.1177/1478210320935671
- Tyng, C. M., Amin, H. U., Saad, M. N., and Malik, A. S. (2017). The influences of emotion on learning and memory. *Front. Psychol.* 8:1454. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01454
- Um, E., Plass, J. L., Hayward, E. O., and Homer, B. D. (2012). Emotional design in multimedia learning. *J. Educ. Psychol.* 104, 485–498. doi: 10.1037/a0026609 UNESCO Education (2020). From Disruption to Recovery. Available online at: <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse>.
- Unger, K. V. (1998). *Handbook on Supported Education: Providing Services for Students with Psychiatric Disabilities*. Towson, MD: Paul H Brookes Publishing Company.
- Van Tilburg, W. A., and Igou, E. R. (2013). On the meaningfulness of behavior: an expectancy x value approach. *Motiv. Emot.* 37, 373–388. doi: 10.1007/s11031-012-9316-3
- Vuilleumier, P. (2005). How brains beware: neural mechanisms of emotional attention. *Trends Cogn. Sci.* 9, 585–594. doi: 10.1016/j.tics.2005.10.011
- Wang, C. J. (2019). Facilitating the emotional intelligence development of students: use of technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK). *J. Hospital. Leis. Sport Tour. Educ.* 25:100198. doi: 10.1016/j.jhlste.2019.100198
- Wang, G., Zhang, Y., Zhao, J., Zhang, J., and Jiang, F. (2020). Mitigate the effects of home confinement on children during the COVID-19 outbreak. *Lancet* 395, 945–947. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30547-X
- Wigfield, A., and Gladstone, J. R. (2019). “What does expectancy-value theory have to say about motivation and achievement in times of change and uncertainty?,” in *Motivation in Education at a Time of Global Change*, eds E. N. Gonida and M. S. Lemos (Bingley: Emerald Publishing Limited), 15–32. doi: 10.1108/S0749-742320190000020002
- Williams, K. C., Morgan, K., and Cameron, B. A. (2011). How do students define their roles and responsibilities in online learning group projects?. *Dist. Educ.* 32, 49–62. doi: 10.1080/01587919.2011.565498
- Williford, H. (2010). *The Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement in Eleventh Graders*. Edmond, OK: MedCrave Group LLC.
- Wu, S., Zhu, W., Wang, Z., Wang, M., and Lan, Y. (2007). Relationship between burnout and occupational stress among nurses in China. *J. Adv. Nurs.* 59, 233–239. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2648.2007.04301.x

- Yang, Y., Li, W., Zhang, Q., Zhang, L., Cheung, T., and Xiang, Y. T. (2020). Mental health services for older adults in China during the COVID-19 outbreak. *Lancet Psychiatry* 7:e19. doi: 10.1016/S2215-0366(20)30079-1
- Yen, T. F. T. (2020). The performance of online teaching for flipped classroom based on COVID-19 aspect. *Asian J. Educ. Soc. Stud.* 8, 57–64. doi: 10.9734/ajess/2020/v8i330229
- Yilmaz, M. (2009). The effects of an emotional intelligence skills training program on the consistent anger levels of Turkish University students. *Soc. Behav. Person.* 37, 565–576. doi: 10.2224/sbp.2009.37.4.565
- Yucha, C. B., Kowalski, S., and Cross, C. (2009). Student stress and academic performance: home hospital program. *J. Nurs. Educ.* 48, 631–637. doi: 10.3928/01484834-20090828-05
- Yusoff, M. S. B., Hadie, S. N. H., and Yasin, M. A. M. (2021). The roles of emotional intelligence, neuroticism, and academic stress on the relationship between psychological distress and burnout in medical students. *BMC Med. Educ.* 21, 1–10. doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-144736/v1
- Zeidner, M., and Matthews, G. (2018). “Grace under pressure in educational contexts: emotional intelligence, stress, and coping,” in *Emotional Intelligence in Education*, eds K. Keefer, J. Parker, and D. Saklofske (Cham: Springer), 83–110. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-90633-1_4
- Zysberg, L., and Raz, S. (2019). Emotional intelligence and emotion regulation in self-induced emotional states: physiological evidence. *Pers. Individ. Dif.* 139, 202–207. doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2018.11.027